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Overview of Qualitative Study on Trafficking in Persons: Implication for National Development in Nigeria

Oladipo, Idowu Filaodun
oladipoidowu29@yahoo.com
08032261899

Department of Social Science and Humanities, School of General Studies in Education, Federal College of Education
Technical (T), Bichi, Kano State, Nigeria

Abstract

This paper deals with overview of qualitative study on trafficking in persons (TIP) and implication for national development in Nigeria. The incidence of human trafficking involving many Nigerians began in 1990s as a result of the decline in the economy of the country and consequent increase in unemployment, poverty, inflation, low wages and general social misery among the masses. This paper therefore highlights poverty, bad leadership, corruption and cultural practices as some of the causes of TIP; and identified the socio-economic consequences and the implication on national development. The paper concludes that the Nigerian government should swiftly endeavour to address the issue of massive unemployment and poverty in the state as well as create enabling environments for entrepreneurship for the citizenry; also the national laws, international conventions and protocols that have legal potencies to curb trafficking must be implemented or strengthened; and finally, fighting human trafficking in Nigeria requires more efforts to create public awareness of the crime, organized counseling, rehabilitation and re-integration program for the victims. The paper therefore recommends that there is need to alleviate poverty among Nigerian families as a way of stemming the tide of human trafficking in the country. It is widely believed that poverty is at the root cause of women and children trafficking in Nigeria society.

Keywords: Trafficking in Person, Consequences, Implication, National, Development

Introduction

Trafficking in persons also known as human trafficking has been a lucrative trade for centuries, but recent opportunities created by globalization have contributed to an increase in the numbers of persons trafficked in Nigeria. The issue of human cross border trafficking is a complex, multi-faceted phenomenon involving multiple stakeholders at the institutional and commercial level. Human trafficking is a demand-driven global business with a huge market for cheap labour which is often confronted with insufficient or unexercised policy framework or trained personnel to prevent it. Virtually no country in Africa is immune from trafficking. It has taken many forms, but in the context of globalization, has acquired shocking new dimensions. It is a complex, multi-faceted phenomenon involving multiple stakeholders at the institutional and commercial level. Trafficking in person has become a major issue in the world today because people are not commodities and should not be sold and also because of the inhuman treatment meted to victims. All over the world trafficking in person exists. It is prevalent in Asia, Latin America, South America and Africa. Slavery, the precursor of human trafficking became an issue in the 19th century following advances in transportation and technology, which resulted in increasing rates of migration. With industrialization came the migration of people from rural to urban areas. Technological advances of 19th century helped to bring about the new and greater international mobility of labour and this made it possible for traffickers to react quickly to the growing demand for sex trade and cheap labour (Badejo, 2016 in Eze&Oli, 2021). The beginning of mass migration and technological development is significant because it is a trend that has continued to the present. Technological advancement and globalisation enabled and encouraged people to migrate to places with better economic and social opportunities. This means that as many people migrate legally, many were forced to migrate illegally in form of human trafficking. Advances in technology and globalisation also made it easier and more efficient for those involved in the trafficking process to network and operate more efficiently.

Nigeria is rich in resources, but political instability and widespread corruption have facilitated trafficking in persons and hindered national development. Nigeria acts as a source, transit and destination country for trafficking men, women and children to Europe, the Middle East and other countries (Mashil, 2005). Nigeria also has acquired a reputation for being one of the leading African countries in human trafficking with cross border and internal trafficking. The Nigerian women, men and children are taken from Nigeria to other countries and they are subjected to hazardous jobs (UNESCO, 2006). The phenomenon

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of trafficking in person in Nigeria especially of young boys, girls, children and women into exploitative sexual and forced labour, has recently began to attract local, national, regional and international attention from world leaders, academics, the mass media, advocacy groups, the clergy and humanity in general. Human trafficking, like money laundering, advanced fee fraud, cyber scams and illicit trade in arms and narcotics has elicited a great concern as a contemporary social problem worldwide (Poulin, 2004).

Human trafficking for the purposes of sexual and other forms of exploitation has become a global business reaping huge profits for traffickers and organized crime syndicates, causing flagrant human rights violations and creating serious problems for governments across the globe. Trafficking in persons represents the world's third largest area of organized crime – after drugs and arms trade. It is an illicit trade that is unbearable to the human heart. The two methods used by traffickers to get their victims are deception and through force. Human trafficking for the purposes of sexual and other forms of exploitation has become a global business reaping huge profits for traffickers and organized crime syndicates, causing flagrant human rights violations and creating serious problems for governments across the globe. Trafficking in persons represents the world's third largest area of organized crime – after drugs and arms trade. It is an illicit trade that is unbearable to the human heart. Trafficking in persons is inhuman, immoral and an offence under the laws. (UNHCR, 2000). The United States government considers trafficking in person to include all the criminal conduct involved in forced labour and sex trafficking, essentially the conduct involved in reducing or holding someone in compelled service (United States Department Report, 2013). Nigeria is a transit and destination country for men, women and children subjected to trafficking in persons, specifically conditions to forced labour and forced prostitution. Trafficked Nigerian men, women and children are recruited from rural areas within the country's borders – women and girls for involuntary domestic servitude and forced commercial sexual exploitation, and boys for forced labour in street vending, domestic servitude, mining, and begging. The children are subjected to domestic servitude, forced labour, sexual slavery through forced marriages and suicide attacks in Nigeria. Within Nigeria, girls are trafficked primarily for domestic servitude and commercial sexual exploitation. Boys are trafficked for forced labour in street vending, agriculture, and as domestic servants. Islamic religious teachers also traffic boys called Almajiri for forced begging (United States Department Report, 2009) Besides prostitution, forced marriage and forced labour, some of the victims are used for rituals, begging and even for organ transplanting (Ndifon, Apori&Ndifon, 2012) Nigerian women and children are taken from Nigeria to Europe, Arabian countries and African countries, primarily Libya, Gabon, Cameroon, Ghana, Chad, Benin, Togo, Niger, Burkina Faso, and the Gambia, for the same purposes. But the recent economic crisis, poverty, social and political conflicts, insurgency, natural disasters and the contemporary climate change have profoundly influenced the alarming dimension with which people are being pulled-up as clients for human traffickers (UNHCR, 2000) It should be pointed out that many are of the opinion that poor economic conditions in Nigeria which concomitantly led to poverty among large concentration of the population. These socio-economic factors coupled with socio-cultural factors such as the breakdown of the extended family system, gender inequality, child fosterage, high fertility and population growth, the widening gap between the rich and the poor, break-down of societal values amongst others, seems to account for trafficking in person in Nigeria. In addition, human trafficking exposes some Nigerian citizens to all forms of inhuman treatment in foreign countries. These include physical assault, rape, detention and in some extreme cases execution. Many Nigerians are also known to be languishing in prisons in some countries of the world due to the misadventure associated with human trafficking. Dangerous journeys expose trafficked victims to injury and even death. While overcrowded and unhealthy conditions, lack of food and water increase the risk of spreading infectious diseases. Finally, human trafficking creates an environment of violence, crime and fear, separates families, destroys social bonds and support networks, and undermines the economic prospects of the country. It equally gives rise to frequent deportation of Nigerian citizens from foreign countries with its associated diplomatic implications.

The menace of human trafficking in Nigerian state has taken an indescribable facet in the last two decades owing to the factors of; massive unemployment, poverty, recession in the economy, conflicts, globalization, existing weak legal system, and inadequate legislation, and political will. Efforts have been made by Nigerian government to tackle this menace of trafficking in person, for instance, Nigeria ratified most of the important international instruments fighting human trafficking and protecting women and children. Among them are the United Nations Convention against Transnational Organized Crime (2000) and the Palermo Protocol in 2001, the United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child and the Optional Protocol to it on the Sale of Children. Nigeria enacted the Trafficking in Persons (prohibition) Law Enforcement and Administration Act 2003 and Child Rights Act 2003 (Huntley, 2013). The National Agency for the Prohibition of Trafficking in Persons (NAPTIP) and other related matters was established to combat human trafficking. However, these initiatives, human trafficking remains a critical problem in Nigeria thus, paints a bad picture of Nigeria in the international community. Despite Nigeria's legislative efforts to combat trafficking, it still thrives in Nigeria. One is of the opinion that there are negative consequences if

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the able body men, women and children are trafficked out of the country and will have compelling effects on socio-economic that have far reaching outcomes on humanity and the society. In actual fact, the physical torture and abuse of victims from the emotional and psychological ordeal witnessed or gone through by victims in the hands of traffickers, and the attendant impacts on such individuals and society are evidently destructive .It is against this background that the paper focused on the overview of qualitative study on trafficking in persons (TIP) and implication for national development in Nigeria.

Concepts of Trafficking in Persons in Nigeria

A more recent but aptly coined term for human trafficking is the nomenclature, ‘trafficking in persons.’ There is a national government agency that is saddled with the responsibility of prohibiting trafficking in persons in Nigeria. It is known as National Agency for Prohibition of Trafficking in Persons (NAPTIP). The concept of Trafficking in Person is defined as all and attempted acts involved in the recruitment, transportation within or across nation’s borders, purchases, sales, transfer, receipt or harbouring of a person involving the use of deception, coercion or debt bondage for the purpose of placing or holding the persons, whether for or not involuntary servitude (domestic, sexual or reproductive) in forced or bonded labour, or in slavery-like conditions. In the same vein, human trafficking according to Article 3(a) of the United Nations Palermo Protocol is conceptualized as recruitment, transportation, transfer, harbouring, and receipt of persons, by means of threat, use of force and other forms of coercion. It also entails use of abduction, fraud, deception, the abuse of power in giving or receiving of payments or benefits to achieve the consent of a person having control over another person for the purpose of exploitation (United Nations Palermo Protocol, 2000). Also, UNESCO (2006) on trafficking in person defined it to be a process which involves the exploitation of a vulnerable person through recruitment, transportation, transfer, harbouring or receipt of persons by means of threat or use of force or other forms of coercion, abduction, fraud, deception and abuse of power.

Trafficking in Persons is a relatively recent term and is used to describe the act of the acquisition or transportation of a person away from the community in which they live through the use of violence, coercion or deception for the purpose of exploiting them. In the case of children, their vulnerability is a factor, thus coercion does not have to be present. United Nations (2013) defines human trafficking in person as:

“the recruitment, transportation, transfer, harbouring or receipt of persons, (male or female) by means of threat or use of force or other forms of coercion, of abduction, of fraud, of deception, of the abuse of power, or of a position of vulnerability, or of the giving or receiving of payments or benefits to achieve the consent of a person having control over another person for the purpose of exploitation. Exploitation shall include at a minimum the exploitation of the prostitution of others or other forms of sexual exploitation forced labour or services, slavery or practices similar to slavery, servitude or the renewal of organs”.

In a similar view, Oloko cited in Okpalakunne (2006) explained that human trafficking consists of both national and trans-national recruitment and movement of persons for the purpose of providing cheap, manipulatable and exploitable labour for domestic and agricultural work, commercial sex work or prostitution, begging, unregulated industrial work and street trading. Adepelumi (2015) argues that trafficking in person is a transnational organized crime that impacts not only on the individual victims but the entire society. Trafficking either occurs within the shores of a country (internal) or outside its shores (external). Internal trafficking involves trafficking of a person from one community or village to another, within the states or outside the states. It is trafficking of persons within a country. The purpose of internal trafficking is usually for domestic labour, child labour, illicit adoption, begging, sexual exploitation, ritual, organ harvesting etc. External trafficking of persons on the other hand is carried out outside the shores of the victim’s country. The menace is seen to have been undermining the national peace, development and security of Nigeria. Trafficking has become socio-economic problems of significant magnitude in Nigeria. Many writers on the subject have suggested some probable causes of this problem. There is an urgent need to determine the veracity of some of the identified causes through this paper.

The Factors Aiding Trafficking in Persons Activities in Nigeria

Socio-economic factors such as poverty, unemployment, economic downturn as the nation is currently undergoing, inadequate educational opportunities etc. fuel human trafficking. All these were the problems that confronted the victims of human trafficking that make them vulnerable to traffickers and their agents. Abiodun, Akinlade and Oladejo (2021) highlight the factor aiding trafficking of persons as follows:

1. In the first instance, victims are made to shift a base from rural areas to urban areas and this is widely known as rural-urban trafficking. Victims in this class are usually trafficked for farming purpose and also there could be rural-rural

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- trafficking a situation where traffickers convey victims from one village or rural area to another. There is also urban-urban trafficking, a situation where traffickers move their victims from one urban area to another.
2. Secondly, there exists the usual tradition of entrusting poor children to more comfortable relatives and this may generate exposure to human trafficking. This is very common in a situation whereby some parents would sell their own children, and it is not just for the monetary gains, but with thought or belief that their children would find their ways out of abject chronic poverty ravaging the land and move to a place where they would live a better life with more prospects.
 3. Also in Nigeria, these women and young girls usually fall victims of being trafficked from their original place of abode to another location or across the national borders having been lured, tricked or deceived that they would be gainfully employed and live an accomplished life. But at the end of the day, they actually get trafficked for commercial sexual exploitation and domestic servitude in foreign lands.
 4. Another striking factor responsible for human trafficking in Nigeria is abject poverty that has ravaged the land. Studies have revealed that over 10 million Nigerian girls and boys are being trafficked across the country's borders due to poverty. The victims are trafficked to different destinations which include; African states of Benin Republic, Mali, among others while the states in the Europe include; United Kingdom, Spain, Italy, Belgium, the Netherlands, and Germany and the United Kingdom respectively.
 5. In recent time, the World Bank report indicated that over 1.8 billion people live in the various nations prone to or engulfed in violent conflict are have been trafficked abroad. So it is established that the Boko Haram, Fulani-herdsmen crisis and armed banditry remain the push factors for trafficking in persons and migration; this is evident in a situation where young male children are being trafficked and used as soldiers and militias and young girls as sex toys by the insurgents. The kidnapped young girls are sold off into slavery and forceful marriage.
 6. In addition, there is a weak legal system in place in the country; ninety percent (90%) of Nigerian borders are porous, government officials are absolutely corrupt in all ramifications, while a large number of Nigerian youths also belong to the various international organized criminal syndicates or networks while the limited capacity or commitment by immigration and law enforcement officers to control borders remain contributory factors to the menace.
 7. There also exists lack or absence of adequate legislation and of political will on the part of Nigerian government to enforce existing legislation or mandates, Acts, and penalties for trafficking offenders that could prohibit all forms of human trafficking.

Causes of Trafficking in Person (Tip) in Nigeria

Trafficking becomes more worsened by conflicts, natural disasters, socio-economic problems, among others, thereby pushing people to seek greener pastures or migrate to other locations for survival (Dodo, 2012). In addition, there are other macro-level reasons or factors associated with human trafficking which include: abject poverty, wars, economic injustice, globalized of the consumer markets, global sex tourism, among others while the micro-level risk factors entail: child abuse and neglect, family breakdown, poor family relations, mental illness, child homelessness, among others (Dodo, 2012).

- i. **Poverty:** Poverty is a state of being poor or lack of basic necessities of live. Poverty can make people vulnerable to human trafficking and child labour. Parents may give up their children to be taken to cities and work as house helps. Some parents may even sell their children totally into slavery while others go to cities or travel abroad to engage in prostitution in order to make money. Apart from poverty, many of the victims of human trafficking abroad particularly women and girls are ignorance of the fate that await them in their country of destination. The situation is such that many of the women and girls had little or no education hence they are easily carried away by the picture of good lives painted by their sponsors. Particularly African and Nigerians with a large concentration of polygamous family for the purpose of egalitarian settlements in the villages and slums where means of livelihood became cumbersome, hence adolescents strive to find solace outside the home, thereby making them vulnerable to the tactics of traffickers (Rotimi, 2001)
- ii. **Greed and Crave for Wealth:** People who are not contented with what they have or those who want to accumulate fast wealth may find themselves engaged in human trafficking. Crave for wealth is another factor. The high propensity to acquire wealth regardless of the legality and morality of the source. Previous 'success' of some trafficked women lured some others into trafficking, unfortunately sources of those 'successes' are unknown until they become victim of prostitution. On coming back home, they were able to acquire land, buy houses, luxurious objects such as gold, necklaces, etc which they would not have been able to afford if they had remained in their villages. The illicit

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- traffickers, on the other hand, were primarily motivated by materialism. Ofido (2000) remarked that the major underlying factor for prostitution is greed. Ruth (2000) contended that the willingness of our ladies to travel abroad and offer themselves for sex trade is equally a pointed to the level of the crave by our youths to do anything for money
- iii. **Bad Leadership and Corruption:** The levels of bad leadership and corruption have led to increase in unemployment rate in Nigeria. To the extent that men and women chose to migrate for labour or sex work because of the realization that Europe and Western nations have a valued currency hence labour and sex will be profitable. The implication is that people choose to work in richer countries in order to improve their economic standing back in Nigeria with a hopeless economic situation. The double explanation was that while job opportunities abound for male migrants in Europe and North America, women migrants who had no access to jobs often take to prostitution as an option. Human traffickers bribe government's officials with money and material things so that they can continue to carry out their business without being caught or hindered by government. In addition to the above, our weak legal system also contributes to the cases of human trafficking. Porous borders, corrupt government officials, the involvement of international organized criminal groups or networks, capacity of or commitment by Immigration and law enforcement officers to control borders; and because of adequate legislation and a political will and commitment to enforce existing legislation or mandates are other factors that facilitate trafficking in persons.
 - iv. **Ignorance:** Ignorance on the part of the victims of human trafficking contributes to the prevalence of the scourge on trafficking in persons. Vulnerable members in the society can easily be deceived by human traffickers who will promise them greener pastures and better lifestyles in the cities or abroad and because everybody wants a better and improved life, they innocently follow these traffickers only to discover that their intention was to exploit and use them to make money. Some of these people may even be forced to take oaths not to disclose their secret or try to escape. Several victims of the scourge, especially boys, girls and children, have claimed ignorance of what bargain they struck until they were caught or eventually taken to Europe to engage in sex trade, illicit drugs and force labour. Ofido (2000) observed that nowadays, Nigerian boys and girls are in overseas countries, mainly Italy, France and Belgium eking out an unreasonable livelihood through prostitution and illicit drugs. She noted that most of the boys and girls were lured into the act by a carted that promised them fabulous jobs but seized their passports when they got to overseas and forced them into prostitution.
 - v. **Unemployment:** This is also another reason for the increasing incidence of human trafficking involving Nigeria women and young boys. Nevertheless, the government should make deliberate efforts to humanise the societal environment through provision of gainful employment and other economic empowerment that will ensure improved living standard for the people.
 - vi. **War, Conflict and Natural Disaster:** During prolonged war, children are forced to join the army and are trained to carry guns and ammunitions. Although this may not be done for money, it is also a form of human trafficking e.g during the Second World War, some Africans were trafficked to Europe so as to fight in the war. Trafficking of persons, conflict and natural disaster can lead to economic instability and lack of human rights, giving traffickers an advantage and making people more vulnerable to human trafficking situations. In conflict zones and wars, some rebel or military groups will use child soldiers and keep sex slaves. Additionally, both conflict and natural disaster can lead people to migrate out of their hometowns and home countries, making them more vulnerable to traffickers, especially if they are looking for work or paying smugglers to get where they want to go. And with increased economic instability, traffickers have opportunities to offer false job offers to people, leading them into trafficking situations.
 - vii. **Demand for Cheap Labour/Demand for Sex:** Basic economics tell us that for a market to form, supply and demand need to exist. The demands for cheap labour and for commercialized sex lead to opportunities for traffickers to exploit people. Traffickers can make a large profit by producing goods and services through cheap or free labour and selling the products or services at a higher price. Commercialized sex is a lucrative market that allows traffickers and pimps to become the only benefits from their victims through an endless cycle of buyers and high prices.
 - viii. **Lack of Human Rights for Vulnerable Groups:** In many countries, groups that are marginalized in society lack institutionalized human rights, which can lead to them to be potential victims of trafficking. Traffickers can prey on these marginalized groups because they lack protection of the law enforcement, their families, and even the society they live in. Also, when countries lack fundamental laws regarding human rights, traffickers feel as though they can get away with what they are doing more easily. A lack of human rights laws can also end in punishment for victims, if the laws and government don't recognize that human trafficking is exploitation of other people.

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- ix. **Lack of Legitimate Economic Opportunities:** When people lack legitimate economic opportunities, which can also lead to increased vulnerability to human trafficking. Groups that are especially vulnerable in this area are migrants without work permits, those who lack education, those who live in rural areas where there are fewer jobs available, as well as women and certain ethnic groups who may not be able to get jobs due to discrimination. Traffickers offer seemingly legitimate jobs to people who cannot get them otherwise, only to lure them into forced labor, sex trafficking, bonded labor, and more.
- x. **Social Factors and Cultural Practices:** In many countries, cultural practices and social factors are a major cause of human trafficking. In some places, bonded labor is seen as an acceptable way to pay off debt. In other places, selling children to traffickers is the norm, especially for poorer families in rural areas. Some countries, such as Mauritania, still practice antiquated slavery, where families are held for generations by slave-masters. There are also instances, like in Uzbekistan, where forced labor is institutionalized. During the cotton harvest, all adults and children are expected to work in the cotton fields until the crops are harvested. Cultural and social factors can also lead victims not to speak up about being trafficked or who their traffickers are, especially if they come from groups who lack human rights protections.
- xi. **Trafficking Generates a Huge Profit:** One major cause of human trafficking is the huge profit that traffickers gain. This is an incentive for them to continue trafficking people in both forced labour and sex trafficking. For traffickers using forced labourers and bonded labourers, they get cheap labour and can sell their product or service at a much higher cost. For those using sex trafficking, they can easily take all of the profit, forcing women to make a certain amount each night, and keeping them in the situation through drugs, violent force, threats, and more.
- xii. **Lack of Safe Migration Options:** For those looking to migrate out of their home countries due to safety concerns or economic opportunities, they are especially vulnerable to traffickers. Traffickers can use illegal smuggling as a way to trick people into forced labor or sex trafficking. And for migrants looking for jobs in other countries, traffickers typically offer them job opportunities that seem legitimate, only to force them into a trafficking situation. For instance, when Russia was preparing for the Olympics, several men from Serbia, Armenia, Azerbaijan, and other nearby countries were promised construction jobs, only to be paid very little and be treated poorly. And many women from countries like Nigeria, Ukraine, and other Eastern European and African countries are offered nanny, house help or restaurant jobs in Western Europe, Asian, Saudi Arabia only to be trapped in sex trafficking and human organ harvest.
- xiii. **Gender-based discrimination** is an all-pervasive reason why women and girls make up the majority of persons who are trafficked. Gender-based discrimination is shown by the low status of women, particularly in developing countries, the lack of education for girls, the expectation of women to perform certain roles and to be solely responsible for her children, and the discrimination against women in political participation, sexuality, religion, customs and social practices. Sexism is imbedded in all institutions of society in general, and particularly in the structure of the labour market and the job opportunities available for women. A feminist perspective to protect the rights of migrant and trafficked persons is important to ensure that responses do not work

Consequences of Trafficking in Persons (Tip) in Nigeria

The consequences of trafficking in persons can be social, political and economic. But as the main focus of this paper is the victim's perspectives, the socio-economic consequence outshines the other one. Most of Nigerians become victims of human trafficking in their process of migration to earn a better livelihood. Earning a better livelihood was an overriding factor for Nigerians' migration in general and trafficking in particular. The end result of trafficking is exploitation of victims for different purposes. Traffickers receive huge amount of money from potential victims and their families too. Trafficking in person exposed some Nigerians to all forms of inhuman treatments in foreign countries. These include physical assault, rape, physical abuse, detention, and in some extreme cases execution. Many Nigerians are also known to be languishing in prisons in some countries of the world due to the misadventure associated with human trafficking. Aondover, (2018) reports that victims are more likely to experience fear, guilt, sense of betrayal, lack of trust, suspicion, sense of apathy, shame, withdrawal, resignation to fate, hopelessness, extreme form of submissiveness, maladaptation, and a sense of loss of personal autonomy; initiative and integrity. It has given rise to frequent deportation of Nigerian citizens from foreign countries with its attendant diplomatic implications.

These consequences are categorized into:

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- 1) **Physical injuries:** These are marks on the body, loss parts of the body. etc such as burns, bruise, wounds, cuts, dislocations etc .which are usually inflicted on the victims through physical abuse and maltreatment. It violates the human right of victims; degrading and dehumanizing. It results in loss of, or deprivation of property rights
 - 2) **Sexual Abuse:** Human trafficking victims are likely to be sexually abused or exploited especially during the process of moving the victims from one location to another. There are usually cases of rape and sexual intercourse between some perpetrators and the victims. E.g., female domestic servants are turned to sex object by their master and his sons, while female master turned the male domestic servants to gigolo or sex partner.
 - 3) **Stigmatization:** The victims of human trafficking are stigmatized when they are with their masters and even when they return home due to inhuman acts they are exposed to. In their master’s house, they are seen and treated as second class citizens.
 - 4) **Health Hazard:** Most of the victims are exposed to health hazards and challenges due to indiscriminate sex which often leads contracting Sexually Transmitted Disease and other deadly diseases like HIV/AIDS. Some may end up with health challenges due to the physical consequences of trafficking.
 - 5) **Death:** Death is the most fatal consequence of human trafficking. Most victims, who have experienced sexual abuse, rape, and have been exposed to health hazards, may end up dying. Some may end up committing suicide.
 - 6) **Loss of Human Resources:** The loss of youths, children, and women will have an effect on the man-power of the nation which will further affect the socio-economic development of the nation. Undermines human capital development potential and promotes money laundering and other financial crimes which can distort the economy.
 - 7) **Separation from Loved Ones:** Children and the victims that are trafficked are separated from their loved ones, thereby denied the mutual love that is supposed to exist among the family members. This can make such victims be hostile in the near future.
 - 8) **Crime:** One of the social consequences is a high rate of crime. The victims due to lack of proper upbringing can get involved in criminal acts such as armed robbery, cultism, prostitution, unruly behavior etc thereby causing social problem in the society. It can bring about a negative image of the country. As an organized crime, it can diversify into other types of crimes like drug trafficking and arm smuggling;
 - 9) **Fear and Anxiety:** These acts of moving people usually bring fear and anxiety hereby causing insecurity in society.
 - 10) **Migration:** Human trafficking involves the movement of people, this brings about migration which in effect populates the urban areas and depopulate the rural areas
 - 11) **Social Disorder:** Victims of human trafficking became maladjusted in society, meaning they fail to cope with the demands of a normal social environment. It can yield future insecurity through social breakdown and exclusion
- Human trafficking has negative consequences on individual, mainly the victims and the society in general.

Conclusion

The problem of trafficking in person has persisted in Nigeria despite several campaigns, conferences, workshops, and seminars organized by the government and NGOs to curb the menace. The menace of trafficking in person is damaging, disastrous and devastating to the victims, the family and the society at large. In view of the pervasive and penetrative effects and consequences trafficking in persons on Nigeria and Nigerians, there is need for a continuous synergy of efforts to curb the menace.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Government should intensify public awareness campaigns on child trafficking by organizing sensitization programmes such as workshops, seminars and campaigns to educate and enlighten both parents and children on the social, emotional and psychological consequences of child trafficking on the victims.
2. Government in particular should make the country attractive to citizens especially the youths through qualitative public education, job creation and provision of social infrastructures, which often constitute the push factor for emigration.
3. Government should also take positive steps to provide employment opportunities for the youth, and create an enabling environment for the private sector to invest and increase employment opportunities.
4. There is need to alleviate poverty among Nigerian families as a way of stemming the tide of human trafficking in the country. It is widely believed that poverty is at the root cause of women and children trafficking in Nigeria society.
5. Ensure the activities of the NAPTIP receive sufficient funding, particularly for prosecuting trafficking offenders and providing adequate care for victims; implement programs for the disarmament, demobilization, and reintegration of former child combatants that take into account the specific needs of child ex- combatants;

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6. Governments, civil-society groups and media houses can liaise to fight this crime by running special broadcasts during major, sports and entertainment events (e.g. World Cup, Cup of Nations UEFA Champions League, Miss Universe, etc.) when it is certain that a large proportion of viewers would get the message.

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